

1 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL**

2
3 **Repeated Evolution of Storage Root and Invasions of Alpine Biome Drove Replicated**
4 **Radiations of the Megadiverse *Corydalis* (Papaveraceae) in the Qinghai–Tibet Plateau**

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54 BioGeoBEARS and the M1-DEC model.

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59 birth-death model based on the *Alto1* and *Alto2* trees, respectively.

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61 model with a prior favoring higher values of γ based on the *Master* tree.

62 FIGURE S12. Net diversification rate variation of *Corydalis* under the multitype birth-death

63 model with a prior favoring low values of γ based on the *Alto1* and *Alto2* trees, respectively.

64 FIGURE S13. Net diversification rate variation of *Corydalis* under the multitype birth-death

65 model with a prior favoring higher values of γ based on the *Alto1* and *Alto2* trees,

66 respectively.

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68 the *Master* tree with the root prior set to equal.

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70 the *Alto1* tree with the Fitzjohn et al. (2009) root prior.

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72 the *Alto1* tree with the root prior set to equal.

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74 the *Alto2* tree with the Fitzjohn et al. (2009) root prior.

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80 FIGURE S21. Summary of region-biome transitions of *Corydalis*.

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82 FIGURE S1. The model set used in phylogenetic path analysis. The arrows indicate casual
83 links between two variables.

84

85 FIGURE S2. ML tree of *Corydalis* inferred from the *Complete* dataset. Numbers near nodes are
86 bootstrap values ($\geq 50\%$) and posterior probabilities (≥ 0.50). Asterisks indicate BS = 100%
87 or PP = 1.0. Classification of Chen et al. (2023) is shown on the right. Non-monophyletic
88 sections recovered in this study are in red.

89

90 FIGURE S3. ML trees of *Corydalis* inferred from the plastome and nrDNA datasets as well as
91 five plastid data subsets. Numbers near nodes are bootstrap values. Details for each dataset
92 see Supplementary Table S3.

93

94 FIGURE S4. Bayesian trees of *Corydalis* inferred from the plastome and nrDNA datasets as
95 well as five plastid data subsets. Numbers near nodes are posterior probabilities. Details for
96 each dataset see Supplementary Table S3.

97

98 FIGURE S5. Chronogram of *Corydalis* inferred from the plastome dataset (*Master* tree).
99 Estimated ages are shown above branches with 95% highest posterior density intervals (blue
100 bars).

101

102 FIGURE S6. Ancestral range reconstruction for *Corydalis* on the *Master* tree using
103 BioGeoBEARS and the M1-DEC model. Colored pie charts on each node show the relative
104 probabilities of alternative ancestral distributions. White arrows and node numbers indicate
105 34 dispersal events among six geographic regions.

106

107 FIGURE S7. Ancestral range reconstruction for *Corydalis* on the *Alto1* tree using
108 BioGeoBEARS and the M1-DEC model. Colored pie charts on each node show the relative
109 probabilities of alternative ancestral distributions. White arrows and node numbers indicate
110 34 dispersal events among six geographic regions.

111

112 FIGURE S8. Ancestral range reconstruction for *Corydalis* on the *Alto2* tree using
113 BioGeoBEARS and the M1-DEC model. Colored pie charts on each node show the relative
114 probabilities of alternative ancestral distributions. White arrows and node numbers indicate
115 34 dispersal events among six geographic regions.

116

117 FIGURE S9. Age estimates for dispersal events in *Corydalis*. The inferred dispersal events
118 between regions summarized from Figure 1i and Supplementary Figure S6 are indicated by
119 colors (same color coded as in Figure 1i). Black dots and horizontal bars represent the mean
120 ages and 95% highest posterior density intervals, respectively. Node numbers are referred as
121 those in Supplementary Figure S6. Three distinct climate states (warm house, cool house, and
122 ice house) are based on Westerhold et al. (2020).

123

124 FIGURE S10. Net diversification rate through time for *Corydalis* estimated under the episodic
125 birth-death model based on the *Alto1* and *Alto2* trees, respectively. Green lines and shaded
126 areas indicate median values and 95% confidence intervals.

127

128 FIGURE S11. Net diversification rate variation of *Corydalis* under the multitype birth-death
129 model with a prior favoring higher values of γ based on the *Master* tree. White arrows
130 indicate dispersal events, as in Figure 1i. Clades A and B indicate the same two clades with

131 significant increase in diversification rates, as in Figure 1k.

132

133 FIGURE S12. Net diversification rate variation of *Corydalis* under the multitype birth-death
134 model with a prior favoring low values of γ based on the *Alto1* and *Alto2* trees, respectively.
135 Clades A and B indicate the same two clades with significant increase in diversification rates,
136 as in Figure 1k.

137

138 FIGURE S13. Net diversification rate variation of *Corydalis* under the multitype birth-death
139 model with a prior favoring higher values of γ based on the *Alto1* and *Alto2* trees, respectively.
140 Clades A and B indicate the same two clades with significant increase in diversification rates,
141 as in Figure 1k.

142

143 FIGURE S14. Ancestral state reconstructions for USO (left) and biome (right) in *Corydalis* on
144 the *Master* tree with the root prior set to equal. Colored pie charts on each node show the
145 relative probabilities of alternative ancestral states.

146

147 FIGURE S15. Ancestral state reconstructions for USO (left) and biome (right) in *Corydalis* on
148 the *Alto1* tree with the Fitzjohn et al. (2009) root prior. Colored pie charts on each node show
149 the relative probabilities of alternative ancestral states.

150

151 FIGURE S16. Ancestral state reconstructions for USO (left) and biome (right) in *Corydalis* on
152 the *Alto1* tree with the root prior set to equal. Colored pie charts on each node show the
153 relative probabilities of alternative ancestral states.

154

155 FIGURE S17. Ancestral state reconstructions for USO (left) and biome (right) in *Corydalis* on

156 the *Alto2* tree with the Fitzjohn et al. (2009) root prior. Colored pie charts on each node show
157 the relative probabilities of alternative ancestral states.

158

159 FIGURE S18. Ancestral state reconstructions for USO (left) and biome (right) in *Corydalis* on
160 the *Alto2* tree with the root prior set to equal. Colored pie charts on each node show the
161 relative probabilities of alternative ancestral states.

162

163 FIGURE S19. Evolutionary correlation test for the SR and the alpine biome based on the *Alto1*
164 and *Alto2* trees, respectively. Probabilities that the rate of gain or loss of a character was
165 dependent on the state of the other character were calculated in RevBayes. $BF > 3.2$
166 represents substantial support, and $BF > 10$ represents strong support.

167

168 FIGURE S20. Results of MuHiSSE analyses with the Herrera-Alsina et al. (2018) root prior. a
169 and b) Variations of net diversification rates for each USO state after averaging equivalent
170 models (a) or all models (b). c and d) Variations of net diversification rates for each biome
171 state under the best-fit model (c) or after averaging all models (d).

172

173 FIGURE S21. Summary of region-biome transitions of *Corydalis*. The transitions among
174 different regions and biomes are inferred using the *Master* tree. Numbers next to arrows
175 indicate the number of transitions.

176 TABLE S1. Information of taxa used in this study. Underground storage organ (USO): RH,

177 rhizome; TA, taproot; TU, tuber; SR, storage root.

Lab ID	Species	Voucher	nrDNA	Plastome	USO
X020	<i>Corydalis acuminata</i>	Wang W et al. SX2005128 (PE)	PV032882	PV077388	RH
X021	<i>C. adiantifolia</i>	FPH-0343 (PE)	PV032883	PV077389	TA
	<i>C. adunca</i>			NC_057183	TA
P186	<i>C. aitchisonii</i>	Zcudova P et al. s.n. (MW)	PV032762	PV077390	TU
P013	<i>C. alexeenkoana</i>	Amirhanov A s.n. (MW)	PV032664	PV077391	TU
P014	<i>C. alpestris</i>	Zernov A 3839 (MW)	PV032665	PV077392	TU
X062	<i>C. ambigua</i>	Gao TG 4386 (PE)	PV032898	PV077393	TU
P015	<i>C. amphipogon</i>	Wang QR & Yan MS 11358 (PE)	PV032666	PV077394	RH
P016	<i>C. ananke</i>	Anonymous 1159 (PE)	PV032667	PV077395	RH
P019	<i>C. angustifolia</i>	Zernov et al. 7028 (MW)	PV032668	PV077396	TU
P022	<i>C. appendiculata</i>	Yu TT 15343 (PE)	PV032669	PV077397	SR
P023	<i>C. aquilegioides</i>	Zhu DH 4046 (PE)	PV032670	PV077398	RH
P025	<i>C. atuntsuensis</i>	Anonymous 9441 (PE)	PV032671	PV077399	SR
P027	<i>C. aurea</i>	Shing KH 64 (PE)	PV032672	PV077400	TA
P029	<i>C. balansae</i>	Wang CM W05378 (PE)	PV032673	PV077401	TA
P033	<i>C. balsamiflora</i>	Zhang YT & Lang KY 04 (PE)	PV032674	PV077402	RH
P034	<i>C. barbisepala</i>	Xie L 04-029 (PE)	PV032908/ PV032909	PV077403	RH
P035	<i>C. benecincta</i>	Tang ZX 609 (PE)	PV032675	PV077404	TU
P756	<i>C. breviostrata</i>	Boufford DE et al. 33664 (PE)	PV032874	PV077405	TA
P041	<i>C. brunneovaginata</i>	He Z & Zhou ZL 12615 (PE)	PV032676	PV077406	RH
P042	<i>C. bulbifera</i>	Yang JS 90-216 (PE)	PV032677	PV077407	SR
P043	<i>C. bulbosa</i>	Frey L & Palkowa A s.n. (PE)	PV032678	PV077408	TU
P045	<i>C. bulleyana</i>	Han YF et al. 81-1074 (PE)	PV032679	PV077409	TA
P046	<i>C. bungeana</i>	Guo CY 20062-023-8 (PE)	PV032680	PV077410	TA
P396	<i>C. bungeana</i>	Peng HW 396 (PE)	PV032865	PV077411	TA
X024	<i>C. buschii</i>	Chen ZD & Xu KX 2107 (PE)	PV032884	PV077412	TU
P048	<i>C. calcicola</i>	Boufford DE et al. 42582 (PE)	PV032681	PV077413	SR
P049	<i>C. calycosa</i>	Qin HN et al. 17074 (PE)	PV032682	PV077414	RH
P051	<i>C. capitata</i>	Zhang XS & Ren YX 5337 (PE)	PV032683	PV077415	RH
P052	<i>C. capnoides</i>	Yang ZZ 03-09 (PE)	PV032684	PV077416	TA
P056	<i>C. caseana</i>	Oswald H et al. 4783 (PE)	PV032685	PV077417	RH
P825	<i>C. cashmeriana</i>	Koelz 86 (P)	PV032881	PV077418	SR
P058	<i>C. casimiriana</i>	Anonymous 751892 (PE)	PV032686	PV077419	TA
P060	<i>C. caucasica</i>	Zernov et al. s.n. (MW)	PV032687	PV077420	TU
P062	<i>C. caudata</i>	Guo CY 2501042-1 (PE)	PV032688	PV077421	TU
P063	<i>C. cava</i>	Zelazny J s.n. (PE)	PV032689	PV077422	TU
P066	<i>C. chaerophylla</i>	Wakabayashi M et al. 29730350 (PE)	PV032690	PV077423	RH
P762	<i>C. chanetii</i>	Yan-57 (PE)	PV032877	PV077424	TA
P069	<i>C. changbaishanensis</i>	Anonymous 585 (PE)	PV032691	PV077425	TA
P758	<i>C. cheilanthifolia</i>	Gan QL 3279 (PE)	PV032876	PV077426	TA
P073	<i>C. chingii</i>	Anonymous 8012 (PE)	PV032692	PV077427	TA
P074	<i>C. chionophila</i>	Lvitzkaya G s.n. (MW)	PV032693	PV077428	TA
P075	<i>C. chrysosphaera</i>	Dong JH 1-092 (PE)	PV032694	PV077429	TA
P078	<i>C. conorhiza</i>	Zernov et al. 5794 (MW)	PV032696	PV077430	TU
P080	<i>C. conspersa</i>	Boufford DE et al. 42312 (PE)	PV032697	PV077431	SR
X025	<i>C. cornuta</i>	Anonymous 1690 (PE)	PV032885	PV077432	TA
P081	<i>C. corymbosa</i>	Li BS & Cheng SZ 00656 (PE)	PV032698	PV077433	RH
P082	<i>C. crassifolia</i>	Pimenov M & Kliukov EV 89 (MW)	PV032699	PV077434	RH
P083	<i>C. crispa</i>	Yang JS 89-034 (PE)	PV032700	PV077435	TA
X027	<i>C. crithmifolia</i>	FPH-0722 (PE)	PV032886	PV077436	RH
P085	<i>C. curviflora</i>	Chang CS et al. SI10946 (PE)	PV032702	PV077437	SR

P084	<i>C. dajingensis</i>	Wu ZL 32557 (PE)	PV032701	PV077438	TU
P088	<i>C. dajingensis</i>	Boufford DE et al. 38495 (PE)	PV032703	PV077439	TU
P091	<i>C. dasyptera</i>	Boufford DE et al. 33535 (PE)	PV032704	PV077440	TA
P092	<i>C. davidii</i>	Boufford DE et al. 33042 (PE)	PV032705	PV077441	RH
P093	<i>C. decumbens</i>	Furuse M 57412 (PE)	PV032706	PV077442	TU
P094	<i>C. degensis</i>	Jia SX 178 (PE)	PV032707	PV077443	SR
P095	<i>C. delavayi</i>	Boufford DE et al. 35137 (PE)	PV032708	PV077444	SR
P096	<i>C. delphinioides</i>	Forrest G 28821 (PE)	PV032709	PV077445	RH
P099	<i>C. densispica</i>	Boufford DE et al. 42265 (PE)	PV032710	PV077446	SR
P764	<i>C. dubia</i>	Anonymous 750734 (PE)	PV032878	PV077447	TA
P104	<i>C. duclouxii</i>	Anonymous 4757 (PE)	PV032712	PV077448	RH
P105	<i>C. ecristata</i>	Anonymous 240 (PE)	PV032713	PV077449	SR
	<i>C. edulis</i>			NC_054239	TA
P107	<i>C. elata</i>	Anonymous 06222 (PE)	PV032714	PV077450	RH
P108	<i>C. ellipticarpa</i>	Jiang S et al. 4953 (PE)	PV032715	PV077451	RH
P109	<i>C. emanueli</i>	Amirhanov A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032716	PV077452	TU
P111	<i>C. esquirolii</i>	Anonymous 6405 (PE)	PV032717	PV077453	RH
P112	<i>C. eugeniae</i>	Liu ZG 4844 (PE)	PV032718	PV077454	SR
X028	<i>C. fangshanensis</i>	Wang W 20040918 (PE)	PV032887	PV077455	TA
P113	<i>C. fargesii</i>	Tan SS 195 (PE)	PV032719	PV077456	TA
P114	<i>C. feddeana</i>	Anonymous 1791 (PE)	PV032720	PV077457	SR
	<i>C. filistipes</i>			MK264349	TU
P117	<i>C. fimbrillifera</i>	Anonymous <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032721	PV077458	TA
P118	<i>C. flabellata</i>	Iokawa Y et al. 20320043 (PE)	PV032722	PV077459	TA
P119	<i>C. flaccida</i>	Anonymous 750295 (PE)	PV032723	PV077460	TA
P121	<i>C. flavula</i>	Haywood MJ 657 (PE)	PV032724	PV077461	TA
P122	<i>C. flexuosa</i>	Zhang SR et al. 0008 (PE)	PV032725	PV077462	RH
P123	<i>C. foetida</i>	Zhou SS 5704 (PE)	PV032726	PV077463	TA
P125	<i>C. foliaceobracteata</i>	Boufford DE et al. 37642 (PE)	PV032727	PV077464	TA
P126	<i>C. formosana</i>	Tateishi et al. <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032728	PV077465	TA
P127	<i>C. fumariifolia</i>	Wu CY 127 (PE)	PV032729	PV077466	TU
P400	<i>C. gamosepala</i>	Peng HW 400 (PE)	PV032868	PV077467	TU
P129	<i>C. gerdae</i>	PE01901404	PV032730	PV077468	RH
P130	<i>C. gigantea</i>	Kharkevich S & Buch T <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032731	PV077469	RH
P132	<i>C. giraldii</i>	Anonymous 5705 (PE)	PV032732	PV077470	TA
P134	<i>C. glaucescens</i>	Mayorov S <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032733	PV077471	TU
P135	<i>C. glaucissima</i>	Ying JS & Hong DY 651176 (PE)	PV032734	PV077472	SR
P136	<i>C. glycyphyllos</i>	Boufford DE et al. 42513 (PE)	PV032735	PV077473	SR
P137	<i>C. gortschakovii</i>	Seregin A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032736	PV077474	TA
P141	<i>C. govaniana</i>	Chang CS et al. NE020830 (PE)	PV032737	PV077475	TA
P143	<i>C. grandicalyx</i>	Chang CS et al. TA082 (PE)	PV032738	PV077476	TU
P144	<i>C. grandiflora</i>	Chu KL 7508 (PE)	PV032739	PV077477	TA
P145	<i>C. grubovii</i>	Gubanov IA <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032740	PV077478	TA
P146	<i>C. gymnopoda</i>	Anonymous 3780 (PE)	PV032741	PV077479	RH
P150	<i>C. hamata</i>	Boufford DE et al. 36027 (PE)	PV032743	PV077480	SR
P151	<i>C. hebephylla</i>	Li X 78195 (PE)	PV032744	PV077481	RH
P153	<i>C. hemidicentra</i>	Yang QE & Yuan Q 092 (PE)	PV032745	PV077482	TU
P154	<i>C. hemsleyana</i>	Anonymous 1074 (PE)	PV032746	PV077483	RH
P156	<i>C. hendersonii</i>	Anonymous 76-8653 (PE)	PV032747	PV077484	TA
P765	<i>C. hepaticifolia</i>	No. 1313 (PE)	PV032879	PV077485	TU
P158	<i>C. heracleifolia</i>	Anonymous 23836 (PE)	PV032748	PV077486	TA
P159	<i>C. heterocarpa</i>	Miyazaki T 1004063 (PE)	PV032749	PV077487	TA
P160	<i>C. heterodonta</i>	Anonymous 229 (PE)	PV032750	PV077488	RH
P161	<i>C. heterothylax</i>	Guan KJ & Wang WC 730 (PE)	PV032751	PV077489	SR
P162	<i>C. hookeri</i>	Anonymous 12495 (PE)	PV032910/ PV032911	PV077490	TA
P164	<i>C. hsiaowutaishanensis</i>	Anonymous <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032752	PV077491	TU

P165	<i>C. huangshanensis</i>	Anonymous 3303 (PE)	PV032753	PV077492	TU
P167	<i>C. humilis</i>	G.MILLS.M.D. <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032754	PV077493	TU
P170	<i>C. impatiens</i>	Kamelin R et al. 2234 (MW)	PV032755	PV077494	TA
P172	<i>C. incisa</i>	Oh BU et al. 120610-018 (PE)	PV032756	PV077495	TA
P173	<i>C. inconspicua</i>	Ekuzba OV <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032757	PV077496	SR
	<i>C. inopinata</i>			NC_052866	TA
P174	<i>C. inopinata</i>	Anonymous 75-8701 (PE)	PV032758	PV077497	TA
P178	<i>C. iochanensis</i>	Han YF & Deng KM 81-1088 (PE)	PV032759	PV077498	RH
P180	<i>C. jingyuanensis</i>	Boufford DE et al. 37729 (PE)	PV032760	PV077499	RH
P184	<i>C. kailiensis</i>	Anonymous 571 (PE)	PV032761	PV077500	RH
P399	<i>C. kiautschouensis</i>	Peng HW 399 (PE)	PV032867	PV077501	TU
P189	<i>C. kingii</i>	Anonymous 7407 (PE)	PV032763	PV077502	TA
P191	<i>C. kiukiangensis</i>	Jin XH et al. DLJ-ET1084 (PE)	PV032764	PV077503	RH
P194	<i>C. kokiana</i>	Anonymous 2757 (PE)	PV032765	PV077504	SR
P198	<i>C. krasnovii</i>	Pimenov M & Kliukov EV <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032766	PV077505	TA
P199	<i>C. kushiroensis</i>	Yamaji H 4982 (PE)	PV032767	PV077506	TA
P200	<i>C. lasiocarpa</i>	Fu GX 251 (PE)	PV032768	PV077507	TA
P766	<i>C. latiflora</i>	PE01901381	PV032880	PV077508	RH
P102	<i>C. laucheana</i>	Guan KJ et al. 242 (PE)	PV032711	PV077509	TA
P204	<i>C. laucheana</i>	Boufford DE et al. 38342 (PE)	PV032769	PV077510	TA
P205	<i>C. laxa</i>	Asplund E <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032770	PV077511	TU
P208	<i>C. ledebouriana</i>	Rusanovich I <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032771	PV077512	TU
P209	<i>C. leptocarpa</i>	Anonymous 8675 (PE)	PV032772	PV077513	TA
P210	<i>C. leucanthema</i>	Peng XB 6050 (PE)	PV032773	PV077514	RH
P211	<i>C. lhasaensis</i>	Zhang YT & Lang KY 1769 (PE)	PV032774	PV077515	TA
P214	<i>C. linarioides</i>	Boufford DE et al. 41086 (PE)	PV032775	PV077516	SR
P217	<i>C. linearis</i>	Wang JF 06300 (PE)	PV032776	PV077517	SR
P218	<i>C. linjiangensis</i>	Li YY et al. 1199 (PE)	PV032777	PV077518	TU
P219	<i>C. linstowiana</i>	Boufford DE et al. 37903 (PE)	PV032778	PV077519	TA
P220	<i>C. livida</i>	Guo BZ & Wang WY 12595 (PE)	PV032779	PV077520	TA
P222	<i>C. longibracteata</i>	Anonymous 76-337 (PE)	PV032781	PV077521	SR
P221	<i>C. longicalcarata</i>	Guan KJ et al. 376 (PE)	PV032780	PV077522	RH
P223	<i>C. lupinoides</i>	Qin HN et al. 237 (PE)	PV032782	PV077523	SR
	<i>C. maculata</i>			MK264348	TU
P225	<i>C. maculata</i>	Kim KJ et al. 2009-0164 (PE)	PV032783	PV077524	TU
P226	<i>C. madida</i>	Lang KY et al. 1238 (PE)	PV032784	PV077525	RH
P228	<i>C. magadanica</i>	Khokhriakov AP <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032785	PV077526	TU
P229	<i>C. mairei</i>	Zhang GM 548 (PE)	PV032786	PV077527	RH
P231	<i>C. marschalliana</i>	Kalashnikova O <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032787	PV077528	TU
P232	<i>C. mayae</i>	Feng KM 6672 (PE)	PV032788	PV077529	SR
P236	<i>C. melanochlora</i>	Anonymous 2789 (PE)	PV032789	PV077530	SR
P237	<i>C. micrantha</i>	Phillippe LR et al. 43162 (PE)	PV032790	PV077531	TA
P239	<i>C. microsperma</i>	Anonymous 6726 (PE)	PV032791	PV077532	RH
P517	<i>C. mildbraedii</i>	CPG30560 (PE)	PV032869	PV077533	TA
P757	<i>C. mira</i>	Li BS 11710 (PE)	PV032875	PV077534	TA
P243	<i>C. moorcroftiana</i>	Gubanov I 804 (MW)	PV032792	PV077535	TA
P244	<i>C. moupinensis</i>	Naito T et al. 431 (PE)	PV032793	PV077536	TA
P245	<i>C. mucronata</i>	Naito T et al. 75 (PE)	PV032912	PV077537	RH
P246	<i>C. mucronifera</i>	Wu YH 1603 (PE)	PV032794	PV077538	TA
	<i>C. namdoensis</i>			MK264350	TU
P248	<i>C. nigroapiculata</i>	Boufford DE <i>s.n.</i> (FI)	PV032795	PV077539	SR
P249	<i>C. nobilis</i>	Tang P A93021 (PE)	PV032796	PV077540	TA
P250	<i>C. nudicaulis</i>	Pimenov M et al. <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032797	PV077541	TU
X033	<i>C. ochotensis</i>	Lu LM 21 (PE)	PV032888	PV077542	TA
P254	<i>C. oligosperma</i>	Ni ZC et al. 1212 (PE)	PV032798	PV077543	SR
P255	<i>C. omeiana</i>	Anonymous e105 (PE)	PV032913/ PV032914	PV077544	RH

X034	<i>C. ophiocarpa</i>	Wang W 40 (PE)	PV032889	PV077546	TA
P256	<i>C. ophiocarpa</i>	Wu JY et al. 70 (PE)	PV032799	PV077545	TA
P258	<i>C. orthopoda</i>	Liu TY & Ho HL 635 (PE)	PV032800	PV077547	TA
P259	<i>C. oxypetala</i>	Tsai HT 53875 (PE)		PV077548	SR
P260	<i>C. pachycentra</i>	Boufford DE et al. 42494 (PE)	PV032915	PV077549	SR
P261	<i>C. pachypoda</i>	Yang JS 88-81 (PE)	PV032801	PV077550	TA
P263	<i>C. paczoskii</i>	Aniskin D <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032802	PV077551	TU
P264	<i>C. paeoniifolia</i>	Kharkevich S et al. <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032803	PV077552	RH
X035	<i>C. pakistanica</i>	FPH-0914 (PE)	PV032921/ PV032922	PV077553	SR
X036	<i>C. pallida</i>	Chen ZD & Xu KX 2062 (PE)	PV032890	PV077554	TA
P266	<i>C. pallidiflora</i>	Amirhanov A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032804	PV077555	TU
P268	<i>C. paniculigera</i>	Pimenov M et al. 53 (MW)	PV032805	PV077556	TA
P269	<i>C. parviflora</i>	Anonymous 5397 (PE)		PV077557	TA
	<i>C. pauciovulata</i>			MK264352	TA
P272	<i>C. petrophila</i>	Anonymous 5314 (PE)	PV032806	PV077558	RH
P273	<i>C. pingwuensis</i>	Jiang S et al. 7145 (PE)	PV032807	PV077559	RH
P274	<i>C. polygalina</i>	Anonymous 751550 (PE)	PV032808	PV077560	SR
P277	<i>C. potaninii</i>	Wang ZB 14530 (PE)	PV032809	PV077561	TA
P278	<i>C. prattii</i>	Liu CS 932 (PE)	PV032810	PV077562	SR
P279	<i>C. pseudoadoxa</i>	Anonymous 3557 (PE)	PV032811	PV077563	SR
P281	<i>C. pseudoadunca</i>	Sochivko A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032812	PV077564	TA
P282	<i>C. pseudobarbisepala</i>	Boufford DE et al. 38483 (PE)	PV032813	PV077565	SR
P077	<i>C. pseudocristata</i>	Song ZP 38588 (PE)	PV032695	PV077566	SR
X037	<i>C. pseudocrithmifolia</i>	FPH-0504 (PE)	PV032891	PV077567	TA
P294	<i>C. pseudodrakeana</i>	Anonymous 3817 (PE)	PV032821	PV077568	TA
P284	<i>C. pseudofluminicola</i>	Wu ZL 32387 (PE)	PV032814	PV077569	SR
P285	<i>C. pseudohamata</i>	Tang XZ 1311 (PE)	PV032815	PV077570	SR
P287	<i>C. pseudoimpatiens</i>	Boufford DE et al. 41861A (PE)	PV032816	PV077571	TA
P288	<i>C. pseudoincisa</i>	Fu KJ 4433 (PE)	PV032817	PV077572	RH
P290	<i>C. pseudolongipes</i>	Anonymous 74-2321 (PE)	PV032818	PV077573	TA
P291	<i>C. pseudomairei</i>	Geng YY et al. 20070259 (PE)	PV032819	PV077574	RH
P292	<i>C. pseudomicrophylla</i>	Anonymous 770052 (PE)	PV032820	PV077575	TA
P295	<i>C. pseudosibirica</i>	Boufford DE et al. 38551 (PE)	PV032822	PV077576	TA
P297	<i>C. pseudotongolensis</i>	Yu SX et al. 5194 (PE)	PV032823	PV077577	TA
P298	<i>C. pseudoweigoldii</i>	Anonymous 12749 (PE)	PV032824	PV077578	RH
P299	<i>C. pterygopetala</i>	Xu LS & Ke R 150113 (PE)	PV032916/ PV032917	PV077579	RH
P300	<i>C. pubicaulis</i>	Naito T et al. 819 (PE)	PV032825	PV077580	SR
P301	<i>C. pumila</i>	Anonymous <i>s.n.</i> (FI)	PV032826	PV077581	TU
P304	<i>C. pygmaea</i>	Luo J et al. LuoJian-ML-028 (PE)	PV032827	PV077582	TA
X040	<i>C. racemosa</i>	Anonymous 883 (PE)	PV032892	PV077583	TA
P519	<i>C. raddeana</i>	Liu B et al. 25454 (PE)	PV032870	PV077584	TA
P307	<i>C. radicans</i>	Yu TT 7435 (PE)	PV032828	PV077585	RH
P520	<i>C. repens</i>	Liu B et al. 5525 (PE)	PV032871	PV077586	TU
P313	<i>C. rostellata</i>	Boufford DE et al. 41368 (PE)	PV032829	PV077587	TA
P521	<i>C. saccata</i>	CPG68494 (PE)	PV032872	PV077588	TU
	<i>C. saxicola</i>			MT077877	TA
P317	<i>C. scaberula</i>	Ho T et al. H.B.G475 (PE)	PV032830	PV077589	SR
P319	<i>C. schanginii</i>	Kliukov EV <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032831	PV077590	TU
P320	<i>C. schelesnowiana</i>	Sochivko A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032832	PV077591	TA
P321	<i>C. schusteriana</i>	Yu TT 822 (PE)	PV032833	PV077592	RH
P323	<i>C. semenowii</i>	Sochivko A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032834	PV077593	TA
P324	<i>C. sewerzowii</i>	Pimenov et al. 81 (MW)	PV032835	PV077594	TU
X042	<i>C. sheareri</i>	Anonymous 679 (PE)	PV032893	PV077595	RH
P326	<i>C. shennongensis</i>	Anonymous 25503 (PE)	PV032836	PV077596	TA
P526	<i>C. shensiana</i>	Peng HW & Zhang J 210821 (PE)	PV032873	PV077597	SR

	<i>C. shensiana</i>			NC_054240	SR
P330	<i>C. sibirica</i>	Gubanov IA 1291 (MW)	PV032837	PV077598	TA
P331	<i>C. sigmantha</i>	Anonymous 1571 (PE)	PV032838	PV077599	TA
P332	<i>C. smithiana</i>	Han YF et al. 81-1089 (PE)	PV032839	PV077600	TA
P333	<i>C. sochivkoi</i>	Sochivko A <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032840	PV077601	TA
P149	<i>C. solida</i>	Anonymous <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032742	PV077602	TU
P339	<i>C. spathulata</i>	Anonymous 6056 (PE)	PV032841	PV077603	TA
P398	<i>C. speciosa</i>	Peng HW 398 (PE)	PV032866	PV077604	TA
P344	<i>C. straminea</i>	Ho T et al. H.B.G286 (PE)	PV032842	PV077605	TA
P347	<i>C. stricta</i>	Gubanov I & Kamelin R 1332 (MW)	PV032843	PV077606	TA
P350	<i>C. taliensis</i>	Dong HJ et al. 931 (PE)	PV032845	PV077607	TA
P351	<i>C. tangutica</i>	Anonymous 191 (PE)	PV032846	PV077608	TU
P352	<i>C. tarkiensis</i>	Mikhailova MA <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032847	PV077609	TU
P348	<i>C. teberdensis</i>	Chubashova <i>s.n.</i> (MW)	PV032844	PV077610	TU
	<i>C. temulifolia</i>			MT920558	RH
P355	<i>C. tenerrima</i>	Anonymous 7829 (PE)	PV032918/ PV032919	PV077611	RH
P358	<i>C. ternata</i>	Sato J 432 (PE)	PV032848	PV077612	TU
	<i>C. ternata</i>			MK264347	TU
P359	<i>C. ternatifolia</i>	Boufford DE et al. 37446 (PE)	PV032849	PV077613	RH
X045	<i>C. thyrsoflora</i>	FPH-1111 (PE)	PV032894	PV077614	SR
P360	<i>C. tianzhuensis</i>	Ho T et al. H.B.G757 (PE)	PV032850	PV077615	TU
P361	<i>C. tibetica</i>	Anonymous76-130 (PE)	PV032851	PV077616	TA
X046	<i>C. tomentella</i>	Wang W 101 (PE)	PV032895	PV077617	TA
	<i>C. tomentella</i>			NC_060366	TA
P363	<i>C. tongolensis</i>	Yu TT 7643 (PE)	PV032852	PV077618	TA
P364	<i>C. trachycarpa</i>	Liu SW 3344 (PE)	PV032853	PV077619	SR
P368	<i>C. trifoliata</i>	Anonymous 73-1115 (PE)	PV032854	PV077620	SR
	<i>C. trisecta</i>			NC_061916	SR
P369	<i>C. trisecta</i>	Yu XL et al. 080077 (PE)	PV032855	PV077621	SR
P370	<i>C. triternatifolia</i>	Yang GP 312 (PE)	PV032920	PV077622	RH
X047	<i>C. turtschaninovii</i>	Chen ZD & Xu KX 2084 (PE)	PV032896	PV077623	TU
X048	<i>C. vaginans</i>	FPH-1214 (PE)	PV032897	PV077624	TA
P377	<i>C. vivipara</i>	Smith H 10120 (PE)	PV032856	PV077625	RH
P381	<i>C. wilsonii</i>	Anonymous386 (PE)	PV032857	PV077626	TA
P382	<i>C. wuzhengyiana</i>	Anonymous 12054 (PE)	PV032858	PV077627	TA
P383	<i>C. yanhusuo</i>	Sun XY 00040 (PE)	PV032859	PV077628	TU
P384	<i>C. yargongensis</i>	Boufford DE et al. 42641 (PE)	PV032860	PV077629	SR
P385	<i>C. yui</i>	Yu TT 7387 (PE)	PV032861	PV077630	TA
P386	<i>C. yunnanensis</i>	Jin XH et al. YN-ET 1660 (PE)	PV032862	PV077631	RH
P387	<i>C. zadoiensis</i>	Yang JS 91-703 (PE)	PV032863	PV077632	SR
P390	<i>C. zhongdianensis</i>	Anonymous 1560 (PE)	PV032864	PV077633	TA
Outgroups					
P076	<i>Ceratocapnos claviculata</i>	Chorley M <i>s.n.</i> (PE)	PV032899	PV035269	
P801	<i>Cryptocapnos chasmophytica</i>	Rechinger KH et al. 352122 (MO)		PV035270	
P603	<i>Cysticapnos pruinosa</i>	Zeyher <i>s.n.</i> (P)	PV032900	PV035271	
X055	<i>Dactylicapnos lichiangensis</i>	CPG24013 (PE)	PV032901	PV035272	
P607	<i>Discocapnos mundii</i>	Drège JF <i>s.n.</i> (P)	PV032902	PV035273	
P422	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	de Nevers G 12676 (PE)	PV032903	PV035274	
P423	<i>Fumariola turkestanica</i>	Pimenov MG et al. 263 (MW)	PV032904	PV035275	
P418	<i>Platycapnos spicata</i>	PE01041997	PV032905	PV035276	
P609	<i>Rupicapnos africana</i>	Humbert H <i>s.n.</i> (P)	PV032906	PV035277	
X085	<i>Sarcocapnos enneaphylla</i>	Anonymous 747827 (KUN)		PV035278	
P800	<i>Trigonocapnos lichtensteinii</i>	Bester SP 7789 (MO)	PV032907	PV035279	

178 TABLE S2. Characteristics of DNA markers used in this study.

DNA marker	Number of sites	Number of taxa
<i>atpA</i>	1521	270
<i>atpB</i>	1500	270
<i>atpE</i>	426	270
<i>atpF</i>	579	270
<i>atpH</i>	243	270
<i>atpI</i>	741	270
<i>ccsA</i>	1011	270
<i>cemA</i>	717	269
<i>clpP</i>	561	243
<i>infA</i>	291	270
<i>matK</i>	1707	270
<i>ndhA</i>	1095	187
<i>ndhB</i>	1542	174
<i>ndhC</i>	372	197
<i>ndhD</i>	1506	205
<i>ndhE</i>	303	242
<i>ndhF</i>	2292	168
<i>ndhG</i>	540	242
<i>ndhH</i>	1227	186
<i>ndhI</i>	525	198
<i>ndhJ</i>	486	198
<i>ndhK</i>	813	188
<i>petA</i>	999	269
<i>petB</i>	645	270
<i>petD</i>	504	268
<i>petG</i>	111	270
<i>petL</i>	93	270
<i>petN</i>	87	270
<i>psaA</i>	2250	269
<i>psaB</i>	2202	270
<i>psaC</i>	243	270
<i>psaI</i>	108	266
<i>psaJ</i>	138	270
<i>psbA</i>	1059	270
<i>psbB</i>	1527	270
<i>psbC</i>	1419	270
<i>psbD</i>	1059	270
<i>psbE</i>	249	270
<i>psbF</i>	117	270
<i>psbH</i>	219	270
<i>psbI</i>	108	270
<i>psbJ</i>	123	270
<i>psbK</i>	189	270
<i>psbL</i>	114	270
<i>psbM</i>	102	270
<i>psbN</i>	129	267

<i>psbT</i>	117	270
<i>psbZ</i>	186	270
<i>rbcL</i>	1425	270
<i>rpl2</i>	879	259
<i>rpl14</i>	366	270
<i>rpl16</i>	408	270
<i>rpl20</i>	342	269
<i>rpl22</i>	363	267
<i>rpl23</i>	267	264
<i>rpl32</i>	144	270
<i>rpl33</i>	243	270
<i>rpl36</i>	111	270
<i>rpoA</i>	1119	270
<i>rpoB</i>	3252	270
<i>rpoC1</i>	2142	270
<i>rpoC2</i>	4371	269
<i>rps2</i>	738	270
<i>rps3</i>	663	270
<i>rps4</i>	574	270
<i>rps7</i>	465	270
<i>rps8</i>	450	270
<i>rps11</i>	459	270
<i>rps12</i>	378	269
<i>rps14</i>	300	265
<i>rps15</i>	273	269
<i>rps16</i>	282	256
<i>rps18</i>	354	267
<i>rps19</i>	288	270
<i>ycf3</i>	510	267
<i>ycf4</i>	552	268
18S rDNA	1791	250
ITS	466	248
26S rDNA	3416	253

179 TABLE S3. Characteristics of eight datasets for phylogenetic analyses.

Dataset	No. taxa	No. sites	Missing data (%)	No. variable/informative sites	GC (%)	Description
<i>Complete</i>	270	61485	4.38	18970/14878	42	76 plastid coding regions (CDS) and nrDNA
Plastome	270	55812	6.82	18392/14451	41	76 plastid CDS
nrDNA	253	5673	1.1	578/427	56	nrDNA
Subset 1	270	5010	-	1599/1291	42	CDS of plastid ATP synthase genes, including <i>atpA</i> , <i>atpB</i> , <i>atpE</i> , <i>atpF</i> , <i>atpH</i> , and <i>atpI</i> .
Subset 2	270	10905	1.11	4953/4096	40	CDS of plastid housekeeping genes, including <i>accD</i> , <i>clpP</i> , <i>infA</i> , <i>matK</i> , <i>rpl2</i> , <i>rpl14</i> , <i>rpl16</i> , <i>rpl20</i> , <i>rpl22</i> , <i>rpl23</i> , <i>rpl32</i> , <i>rpl33</i> , <i>rpl36</i> , <i>rps2</i> , <i>rps3</i> , <i>rps4</i> , <i>rps7</i> , <i>rps8</i> , <i>rps11</i> , <i>rps12</i> , <i>rps14</i> , <i>rps15</i> , <i>rps16</i> , <i>rps18</i> , and <i>rps19</i> .
Subset 3	268	10701	25.88	2663/1857	38	CDS of plastid NADH dehydrogenase-like genes, including <i>ndhA</i> , <i>ndhB</i> , <i>ndhC</i> , <i>ndhD</i> , <i>ndhE</i> , <i>ndhF</i> , <i>ndhG</i> , <i>ndhH</i> , <i>ndhI</i> , <i>ndhJ</i> , and <i>ndhK</i> .
Subset 4	270	10884	0.09	4365/3464	41	CDS of plastid-encoded RNA polymerase (PEP) genes, including <i>rpoA</i> , <i>rpoB</i> , <i>rpoC1</i> , and <i>rpoC2</i> .
Subset 5	270	18312	0.2	4812/3743	42	CDS of plastid photosynthesis-related genes, including <i>cemA</i> , <i>ccsA</i> , <i>petA</i> , <i>petB</i> , <i>petD</i> , <i>petG</i> , <i>petL</i> , <i>petN</i> , <i>psaA</i> , <i>psaB</i> , <i>psaC</i> , <i>psaI</i> , <i>psaJ</i> , <i>psbA</i> , <i>psbB</i> , <i>psbC</i> , <i>psbD</i> , <i>psbE</i> , <i>psbF</i> , <i>psbH</i> , <i>psbI</i> , <i>psbJ</i> , <i>psbK</i> , <i>psbL</i> , <i>psbM</i> , <i>psbN</i> , <i>psbT</i> , <i>psbZ</i> , <i>rbcL</i> , <i>ycf3</i> , and <i>ycf4</i> .

180 TABLE S4. Partitioning scheme and best-fit DNA substitution models.

Best-fit model	No. sites	Partition name
GTR+I+G	1129	rpl14_codon1, atpA_codon1, atpB_codon1
GTR+I+G	1284	atpB_codon2, atpA_codon2, rpl14_codon2, rps7_codon2
GTR+G	1114	petL_codon3, rpl33_codon3, petA_codon3, ndhJ_codon3, atpA_codon3
GTR+I+G	765	infA_codon3, petD_codon3, atpB_codon3
GTR+I+G	142	atpE_codon1
GTR+I+G	807	ycf3_codon2, petA_codon2, ndhJ_codon2, atpE_codon2
GTR+G	181	psbT_codon3, atpE_codon3
GTR+G	241	rpl32_codon3, atpF_codon1
GTR+G	284	rps15_codon2, atpF_codon2
GTR+G	1943	rpl2_codon3, rpoC2_codon3, atpF_codon3
GTR+I+G	637	petD_codon1, petB_codon1, rps14_codon2, petG_codon1, atpH_codon1, psbI_codon1
GTR	241	atpH_codon2, psbF_codon2, psbE_codon2, psbL_codon2
GTR+G	514	rpl36_codon3, rps15_codon3, atpH_codon3, rps4_codon3, rpl20_codon3
GTR+I+G	1783	atpI_codon1, psbN_codon1, ndhH_codon1, rpoB_codon1
GTR+I+G	1055	psbN_codon2, psaJ_codon2, atpI_codon2, petG_codon2, ndhB_codon2, petD_codon2
GTR+I+G	1181	psaA_codon3, atpI_codon3, ycf4_codon3
GTR+I+G	1101	ndhF_codon1, ccsA_codon1
GTR+I+G	1740	ndhE_codon2, ccsA_codon2, psbI_codon2, ndhF_codon2, ndhD_codon2
GTR+G	667	ccsA_codon3, psbZ_codon1, cemA_codon2, petN_codon3
GTR+G	275	cemA_codon1, psaI_codon1
GTR+G	414	cemA_codon3, ndhI_codon3
GTR+I+G	187	clpP_codon1
GTR+I+G	187	clpP_codon2
GTR+I+G	187	clpP_codon3
GTR+G	274	rps19_codon1, rpl33_codon1, infA_codon1
GTR+I+G	198	ndhE_codon1, infA_codon2
GTR+I+G	808	rpl20_codon1, psaI_codon3, matK_codon1, rpl23_codon3
GTR+I+G	814	matK_codon2, psbI_codon3, psbF_codon3, ndhC_codon3, psaJ_codon3
GTR+I+G	569	matK_codon3
GTR+I+G	365	ndhA_codon1
GTR+G	777	ndhA_codon2, psbH_codon2, ndhG_codon2, psbM_codon2, psbK_codon2, psbZ_codon2
GTR+G	1387	ndhK_codon3, rpoC1_codon3, ndhA_codon3, petG_codon3
GTR+I+G	684	ndhB_codon1, ycf3_codon1
GTR+G	958	ndhC_codon2, rps12_codon3, rps7_codon3, psbT_codon2, ndhB_codon3
GTR+G	470	ndhJ_codon1, ndhC_codon1, ycf4_codon1
GTR+I+G	502	ndhD_codon1
GTR+I+G	1266	ndhD_codon3, ndhF_codon3
GTR+G	226	ndhE_codon3, psbK_codon3, psbZ_codon3

GTR+I+G	2090	ndhK_codon2, psaJ_codon1, psbK_codon1, rpoC2_codon2, ndhG_codon1, psbH_codon1
GTR+G	180	ndhG_codon3
GTR+G	809	psbJ_codon1, ycf4_codon2, ndhH_codon2, ndhI_codon2
GTR+I+G	1912	rps14_codon3, rpoB_codon3, ndhH_codon3, rps2_codon3, psbH_codon3
SYM+I+G	1791	18S rDNA
GTR+I+G	466	ITS
GTR+I+G	3416	26S rDNA

181 TABLE S5. Marginal-likelihood estimates and Bayes factor testing results ($2\ln\text{BF}$) of four
182 clock models in BEAST analyses. $2\ln\text{BF}$ was calculated by marginal-likelihood estimates
183 derived from path sampling implemented in BEAST. A $2\ln\text{BF} = 0-2$ represents “not worth
184 more than a bare mention”, $2\ln\text{BF} = 2-6$ represents “positive” evidence, >6.00 represents
185 strong evidence, and >10.00 represents very strong evidence (Kass and Raftery 1995). The
186 value in bold indicates the best-fit clock model.

Clock model	Marginal likelihood	$2\ln\text{BF}$
Strict	-465923.25	469.64
Exponential	-465722.37	67.88
Lognormal	-465688.43	N/A
Random	-465745.66	114.46

187 TABLE S6. Marginal-likelihood estimates and Bayes factor testing results ($2\ln\text{BF}$) of two tree
188 priors in BEAST analyses. $2\ln\text{BF}$ was calculated by marginal-likelihood estimates derived
189 from path sampling implemented in BEAST. A $2\ln\text{BF} = 0-2$ represents “not worth more than
190 a bare mention”, $2\ln\text{BF} = 2-6$ represents “positive” evidence, >6.00 represents strong
191 evidence, and >10.00 represents very strong evidence (Kass and Raftery 1995). The value in
192 bold indicates the best-fit tree prior.

Tree prior	Marginal likelihood	$2\ln\text{BF}$
Yule	-465701.94	27.02
Birth-death	-465688.43	N/A

193 TABLE S7. Dispersal multiplier matrix for the M1 scenario. Three time slices were defined
 194 following Couvreur et al. (2011). Dispersal multipliers between regions were set according to
 195 Ebersbach et al. (2017): 1 = adjacent areas, 0.5 = areas separated by intermittent barriers (e.g.,
 196 land bridge and seaway) or another one area, 0.1 = areas separated by intermittent barriers
 197 and another one area; 0.01 = very unlikely or no dispersal. Geological events considered here
 198 included the breakup of the North Atlantic Land Bridge in the latest Eocene or early
 199 Oligocene (Tiffney 1985), the closure of the Turgai Strait in the early Oligocene (Rögl 1998),
 200 the collision between the Arabian and Eurasian plates since ~35 Ma (Rögl 1998; Mouthereau
 201 et al. 2012), and the opening of the Bering Strait near the Miocene-Pliocene boundary
 202 (Marincovich and Gladenkov 2001; Gladenkov et al. 2002). A, Europe; B, North Asia; C,
 203 Qinghai–Tibet Plateau; D, East Asia; E, East Africa; F, North America.

Region	A	B	C	D	E	F
5–0 Ma						
A	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.01
B	1	1	1	1	0.1	0.01
C	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.01
D	0.5	1	1	1	0.1	0.01
E	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	1	0.01
F	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
30–5 Ma						
A	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.1
B	1	1	1	1	0.1	0.5
C	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.1
D	0.5	1	1	1	0.1	0.1
E	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	1	0.01
F	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.01	1
> 30 Ma						
A	1	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5
B	0.5	1	1	1	0.01	0.5
C	0.5	1	1	1	0.01	0.1
D	0.1	1	1	1	0.01	0.1
E	0.1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
F	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.01	1

204 TABLE S8. Comparison of three transition models in ancestral USO and biome reconstructions
 205 separately based on three chronograms. The values in bold indicate the best-fit transition
 206 model.

	<i>Master tree</i>		<i>Alto1 tree</i>		<i>Alto2 tree</i>	
	AICc	<i>P</i> value	AICc	<i>P</i> value	AICc	<i>P</i> value
USO						
ER	294.88	0.00125	294.24	0.000936	293.28	0.00105
SYM	285.23	N/A	284.18	N/A	285.44	N/A
ARD	290.12	0.02151	289.32	0.01431	290.02	0.04568
Biome						
ER	280.32	3.67×10^{-7}	282.47	2.69×10^{-7}	280.94	2.65×10^{-7}
SYM	269.44	3.88×10^{-5}	270.34	3.58×10^{-5}	270.82	3.24×10^{-5}
ARD	253.08	N/A	253.88	N/A	252.94	N/A

207 TABLE S9. Comparison between the alternative hypotheses. *P* values were estimated with
 208 Tree-Puzzle and Consel. “*P* < 0.01” indicates the alternative topology differing significantly
 209 from the *Master* tree, and should be rejected.

Hypothesis	$\Delta\ln L$	<i>P</i> value				
		AU	KH	SH	WKH	WSH
<i>Alto1</i>	11.93	0.230	0.196	0.773	0.196	0.583
<i>Alto2</i>	15.64	0.153	0.128	0.631	0.128	0.398

210 TABLE S10. Comparison of estimated ages (Ma) for major nodes among three BEAST
 211 analyses. HPD, highest posterior density.

Node	Age (95% HPD)		
	<i>Master</i> tree	<i>Alto1</i> tree	<i>Alto2</i> tree
Crown group of <i>Corydalis</i>	41.44 (34.74–48.71)	41.77 (34.41–48.94)	41.81 (35.00–48.78)
Crown group of subg. <i>Bipapillatae</i>	5.00 (1.97–8.85)	3.66 (1.30–7.04)	5.00 (1.90–9.33)
Crown group of subg. <i>Cremlnocapnos</i>	7.25 (4.59–9.77)	6.60 (4.29–9.41)	6.23 (4.19–8.38)
Crown group of subg. <i>Sophorocapnos</i>	21.27 (14.61–27.94)	22.80 (15.83–31.27)	20.50 (13.82–27.94)
Crown group of subg. <i>Corydalis</i>	31.74 (25.69–37.47)	32.02 (26.03–38.05)	30.39 (24.42–36.02)
Stem group of subg. <i>Corydalis</i>	36.01 (29.46–42.64)	36.23 (29.69–42.91)	35.49 (28.61–42.17)

212 TABLE S11. Comparison of the fit of three different biogeographic models on the three
 213 chronograms under two dispersal scenarios (M0 and M1). M0: equal dispersal probabilities
 214 between pairs of regions; M1: constrained dispersal probabilities based on the connectivity
 215 between two regions (see Supplementary Table S7). d , rate of range expansion; e , rate of
 216 range contraction. The values in bold indicate the best-fit biogeographic model.

Chronogram	Model	$\ln L$	d	e	AICc	$\Delta AICc$
<i>Master tree</i>	M0					
	DEC	-278.27	0.0071	0.0017	560.51	0
	DIVA-like	-291.01	0.0078	0.0000	585.99	25.48
	BayArea-like	-370.15	0.0109	0.0099	744.27	183.76
	M1					
	DEC	-267.88	0.0095	0.0018	539.71	0
	DIVA-like	-278.25	0.0099	0.0000	560.42	20.71
	BayArea-like	-324.39	0.0111	0.0348	652.88	113.17
	<i>Alto1 tree</i>	M0				
DEC		-281.92	0.0071	0.0024	566.55	0
DIVA-like		-292.05	0.0072	0.0000	591.23	24.65
BayArea-like		-368.77	0.0096	0.0114	750.67	184.12
M1						
DEC		-269.43	0.0096	0.0026	546.91	0
DIVA-like		-279.64	0.0095	0.0000	567.34	20.43
BayArea-like		-334.73	0.0094	0.0318	683.15	136.24
<i>Alto2 tree</i>		M0				
	DEC	-279.13	0.0065	0.0025	564.13	0
	DIVA-like	-289.95	0.0073	0.0000	585.64	21.48
	BayArea-like	-372.24	0.0102	0.0106	750.75	186.62
	M1					
	DEC	-269.69	0.0098	0.0025	544.42	0
	DIVA-like	-280.12	0.0094	0.0000	566.39	21.97
	BayArea-like	-336.03	0.0094	0.0359	678.37	133.95

217 TABLE S12. Ancestral range states of the nodes of interests based on the three chronograms.
 218 Node numbers correspond to those in Supplementary Figure S6. A, Europe; B, North Asia; C,
 219 Qinghai–Tibet Plateau; D, East Asia; E, East Africa; F, North America.

Node	<i>Master tree</i>	<i>Alto1 tree</i>	<i>Alto2 tree</i>
1	BC	BC	BC
2	CD	CD	CD
3	CD	CD	CD
4	CD	CD	CD
5	CD	CD	CD
6	BD	BD	BD
7	BF	BF	BF
8	BD	BD	BD
9	BC	BC	BC
10	BF	BF	BF
11	BC	BC	BC
12	AC	AC	AC
13	AC	AC	AC
14	ACD	ACD	ACD
15	AC	AC	AC
16	BC	BC	BC
17	BD	BD	BD
18	BC	BC	BC
19	BC	BC	BC
20	AB	AB	AB
21	BD	BD	BD
22	BD	BD	BD
23	BD	BD	BD
24	BC	BC	BC
25	CD	CD	CD
26	BD	BD	BD
27	CE	CE	CE
28	CD	CD	CD
29	BC	BC	BC
30	CD	CD	CD
31	CD	CD	CD
32	CD	CD	CD
33	CD	CD	CD
34	CD	CD	CD

220 TABLE S13. Comparison of the fit of twelve models in MuHiSSE analyses. Root prior
 221 assumptions were set according to the procedure described by Fitzjohn et al. (2009) or
 222 Herrera-Alsina et al. (2018). Models within 4 AIC units of the best model are shown in bold.
 223 e , extinction fraction.

Model	USO			Biome		
	lnL	AICc	Δ AICc	lnL	AICc	Δ AICc
Fitzjohn et al. (2009) root prior						
Null	-777.52	1584.84	0	-796.82	1623.43	0
MuSSE, equal e	-774.58	1585.81	0.97	-796.29	1629.24	5.81
MuSSE, unequal e	-773.68	1591.04	6.20	-794.79	1633.27	9.84
MuHiSSE, equal e	-760.14	1599.40	14.56	-783.42	1645.97	22.54
MuHiSSE, unequal e	-755.80	1610.24	25.40	-777.60	1653.83	30.40
MuCID2	-761.72	1589.38	4.54	-783.98	1633.90	10.47
MuCID3	-758.78	1622.01	37.17	-779.30	1663.05	39.62
MuCID4	-753.39	1655.40	70.56	-777.28	1703.18	79.75
MuCID5	-753.58	1706.92	122.08	-774.59	1748.94	125.51
MuCID6	-753.26	1766.22	181.38	-774.92	1809.54	186.11
MuCID7	-753.29	1837.46	252.62	-774.42	1879.72	256.29
MuCID8	-752.58	1922.01	337.17	-773.01	1962.88	339.45
Herrera-Alsina et al. (2018) root prior						
Null	-777.53	1584.85	0	-796.81	1623.42	0
MuSSE, equal e	-774.61	1585.86	1.01	-796.28	1629.22	5.80
MuSSE, unequal e	-773.66	1591.01	6.16	-794.79	1633.27	9.85
MuHiSSE, equal e	-758.29	1595.71	10.86	-781.33	1641.79	18.37
MuHiSSE, unequal e	-756.19	1611.02	26.17	-777.77	1654.18	30.76
MuCID2	-761.77	1589.48	4.63	-783.77	1633.48	10.06
MuCID3	-756.66	1617.79	32.94	-780.17	1664.79	41.37
MuCID4	-752.65	1653.91	69.06	-779.18	1706.97	83.55
MuCID5	-754.04	1707.84	122.99	-775.09	1749.95	126.53
MuCID6	-753.87	1767.43	182.58	-774.67	1809.04	185.62
MuCID7	-753.75	1838.39	253.54	-773.26	1877.41	253.99
MuCID8	-753.80	1924.45	339.60	-774.14	1965.12	341.70

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Figure S1

Figure S2

Figure S3

Figure S4

Plastome

nrDNA

Subset 1

Subset 2

Subset 3

Subset 4

Subset 5

Figure S5

Figure S6

Subg. *Corydalis*

Subg. *Sophorocarpus*

Subg. *Cremnocarpus*

Subg. *Bipillatae*

Figure S7

Figure S9

Figure S10

Alto1 tree

Alto2 tree

Figure S11

Figure S12

Alto1 tree

Alto2 tree

Figure S13

Figure S16

Figure S18

Figure S19

Figure S20

Figure S21

